

Supporting Information

Efficient catalytic conversion of ethanol to 1-butanol via the Guerbet reaction over copper- and nickel-doped porous metal oxides

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Information about materials, reagents and solvents.

Ethanol (Dehydrated) was purchased from Biosolve BV, The Netherlands. 1-propanol (99%), 1-butanol (99%), 1-pentanol (99%), 1-hexanol (99%) were purchased from TCI EUROPE N.V.. THF (99.5%) was purchased from Boom BV. $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\geq 98\%$), $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\geq 99.0\%$), $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($> 99.0\%$) were purchased from Alfa Aesar. $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (98%), Decane ($\geq 99.0\%$) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. All chemicals were used as received without further purification.

Leaching test

After reaction, the liquid sample as well as the catalyst was quantitatively transferred to a 50 mL centrifuge tube. Additional THF was used to wash the reactor and recover all catalyst residues (up to 10 mL total volume). After centrifugation, 1ml of the solution was transferred to a glass vial and evaporates all the liquid using rotary evaporator. Then 7ml HNO_3 was added to dissolve all the metal and analyzed by Perkin Elmer instrument (Optima 7000DV).

Recycling test

After a typical catalytic run (0.1 g $\text{Cu}_{10}\text{Ni}_{10}\text{-PMO}$, 3 mL ethanol, 310 °C, 6 h), the catalyst was separated from the reaction solution by centrifugation and subsequent decantation. The solid was additionally washed with THF (2×10 mL), then with acetone (1×10 mL), and dried overnight at room temperature under vacuum prior to the next run.

Analysis of products

After reaction, the solids were separated by filtration and the composition of the liquid phase was analyzed by GC-MS and GC-FID. Besides the main product 1-butanol, a variety of other compounds were detected, which were comprehensively analyzed. Compounds with a similarity match higher than 80% based on GC-MS identification are listed in Table S2 and all these compounds accounted for a total area percentage $> 95\%$ in all samples. Quantification was carried out by GC-FID with the use of calibration curves and decane as internal standard and the calibrated compounds accounted for $> 90\%$ of total products in all samples. Conversion and yield values were calculated based on the equations shown in the quantification part. The gas phase of a reaction with $\text{Cu}_{10}\text{Ni}_{10}\text{-PMO}$ was analyzed by GC-TCD after reaction using a 25mL Parr reactor (reaction conditions: 10 ml ethanol and 0.3g $\text{Cu}_{10}\text{Ni}_{10}\text{-PMO}$ catalyst, 300 °C, 6h). During the reaction, the pressure increased to 80 bar at 300 °C and read 40 bar when cooling to room temperature which indicates the formation of volatile products during reaction as well. Main compounds in the gas phase included: methane, ethylene, ethane, propane, H_2 , CO, and CO_2 .

Quantification

The yield (Y_i) of products was calculated based on the number of carbon atoms in the product as follows, where n_i represents the number of carbons and C_i is the molar concentration of the compound i , C_{EtOH} indicates concentration of ethanol before the reaction assuming the dilution with THF.

$$Y_i = \frac{n_i * C_i}{2 * C_{EtOH}}$$

Conversion was based on the number of carbon atoms in the compounds according to the equations below, where C_{EtOH} indicates concentration of ethanol before the reaction (assuming the dilution with THF) and C'_{EtOH} indicates concentration of ethanol after the reaction.

$$\text{Conversion} = 1 - \frac{C'_{EtOH}}{C_{EtOH}}$$

The selectivity of 1-butanol was defined as

$$\text{Selectivity (BuOH)} = \frac{n_{BuOH} * C_{BuOH}}{\sum_i n_i C_i}$$

It should be pointed out that we identified most of the products in the liquid phase based on the GC-MS analysis (see table s1). The carbon balance (C) was in the range 68%-99%, accounting for a loss of carbon materials in the gas phase and partly to the loss of liquid during transfer after reaction. The carbon balance was calculated as follows

$$C = \frac{2C'_{EtOH} + \sum_i n_i C_i}{2C_{EtOH}}$$

Space time yield (STY) of 1-butanol was calculated as follows, where N_{EtOH} is the number of moles of ethanol before reaction, Y_{BuOH} is the yield of 1-Butanol, M_{BuOH} is the molar mass of 1-Butanol, $W_{cat.}$ is the weight of catalyst and T is the reaction time.

$$STY = \frac{N_{EtOH} * Y_{BuOH} * M_{BuOH}}{2 * W_{cat.} * T}$$

Table S1 Selected examples of heterogeneous catalysts for the Guerbet-coupling of ethanol to 1-butanol.

Catalyst	Tem. (°C)	Operation mode	GHSV (std cm ³ g _{cat} ⁻¹ h ⁻¹) or Time (h) ^a	Conv. %	1-butanol Yield %	STY (g _{pro} kg _{cat} ⁻¹ h ⁻¹) ^b	Ref.
MgO	450	Continuous	n.a.	56	18	-	1
MgO	400	Continuous	n.a.	60	6	-	2 ^c
Mg ₃ AlO _x	300	Continuous	n.a.	19	4.5	-	3
Mg ₃ AlO _x	350	Continuous	~960	35	14	~400 ^d	4
Mg ₃ Fe _n Al _{1-n} O _x	350	Continuous	~1000	50	10	~220 ^d	5,6
Ca _{1.64} -P HAP	350	Continuous	~880	26	18	~470 ^d	7
HAP	330	Continuous	n.a.	17	11	-	8 ^c
Ca _{1.67} -P HAP	275	Continuous	n.a.	8.2	6.7	-	9 ^c
HAP	340	Continuous	n.a.	6.6	5	-	10 ^c
HAP	298	Continuous	2000	20	14	-	11 ^c
HAP-CO ₃	400	Continuous	1000	40	22.4	-	12
Sr _{1.7} -P HAP	300	Continuous	~570	11	9	~160 ^d	13
CuMgAlO _x	200	Batch	5	4.1	1.6	203.4 ^d	14,15
PdMgAlO _x	200	Batch	5	3.8	2.9	368.6 ^d	14
Ni-Mg/Al	300	Continuous	n.a.	83	-	-	16 ^e
Mg ₃ AlO _x	300	Continuous	n.a.	44.1	19.7	-	17 ^e
Cu-Mg/Al	n.a.	Continuous	n.a.	68	39	-	18 ^e
Co Powder	200	Batch	72	4	2.9	7.6 ^f	19
Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	230	Batch	22.4	41	19.5	187.0 ^f	20
Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	250	Batch	72	27	22	78.8 ^d	21
Cu-CeO ₂	330	Continuous	n.a.	67	30	-	22
Cu10Ni10-PMO	320	Batch	6	56	22	704.6^f	This work

a. GHSV = alcohol gas-hourly space velocity at (298 K, 101 kPa), inert gas excluded. b. Space time yield of 1-butanol. c. Mechanistic details also given. d. numbers come from the review paper (Catal. Sci. Technol.,2015, 5, 3876–3902). e. results from patent. f. numbers calculated based on equation at page s4.

Table S2 Selected examples of heterogeneous catalysts for the Guerbet-coupling of ethanol to 1-butanol in batch reactor.

Catalyst	Tem. (°C)	Catalyst loading ^a	Reaction Time (h)	Conv. %	1-butanol Yield %	1-butanol Selectivity %	STY (g _{pro} kg _{cat} ⁻¹ h ⁻¹) ^b	Ref.
CuMgAlO _x	200	1.3%	5	4.1	1.6	40.3	203.4 ^a	14,15
PdMgAlO _x	200	1.3%	5	3.8	2.9	72.7	368.6 ^a	14
Co Powder	200	4.3%	72	4	2.9	69	7.6 ^b	19
Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	230	4.0%	22.4	41	19.5	47.5	187.0 ^a	20
Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	250	4.2%	72	27	22	80	78.8 ^a	21
Cu10Ni10-PMO	320	4.2%	6	56	22	70	704.6^b	This work

a. numbers come from the review paper (Catal. Sci. Technol.,2015, 5, 3876–3902). b. numbers calculated based on equation at page s4.

Table S3 Elemental composition of Cu-M-PMO catalysts determined by ICP analysis.

Cat.	Al (wt.%)	Cu (wt.%)	Mg (wt.%)	Ni (wt.%)
MgAl-PMO	12.4	-	32.6	-
Cu20-PMO	11.3	15.4	24.0	-
Ni20-PMO	12.9	-	23.9	16.8
Cu13Ni7-PMO	12.4	11.7	24.3	5.4
Cu10Ni10-PMO	11.6	8.2	24.5	7.5
Cu7Ni13-PMO	12.0	5.6	24.7	8.7

Table S4 GC-MS analysis of the products.

Retention time (min.)	Area Percentage %	Compound name	Similarity	Compound structure
3.21	0.31	Acetaldehyde	83	
3.3	0.24	Pentane	87	
3.48	0.22	Ether	91	
* 4.01	49.71	Ethanol	91	
5.24	0.52	Butanal	95	
* 5.33	1.6	Ethyl Acetate	91	
5.58	0.18	Heptane	90	
5.93	0.25	2-Butanol	90	
* 9.2	27.01	1-Butanol	93	
9.6	0.1	2-Pentanol	83	
10.94	0.11	Butanal, 2-ethyl-	91	
12.16	1.1	Butanoic acid, ethyl ester	97	
12.58	0.17	3-Hexanone	91	
* 13.1	0.59	Acetic acid, butyl ester	90	
13.74	0.12	3-Hexanol	90	
* 16.91	1.73	1-Butanol, 2-ethyl-	90	
17.02	0.1	4-Heptanone	90	
* 18.83	7.72	1-Hexanol	83	
© 19.17	1.78	Decane	96	
22.38	0.35	Butanoic acid, butyl ester	90	
22.58	0.35	Hexanoic acid, ethyl ester	97	
23.57	0.14	Acetic acid, hexyl ester	90	
* 26.35	0.62	1-Hexanol, 2-ethyl-	83	
* 28.68	1.85	1-Octanol	91	
32.32	0.1	Octanoic acid, ethyl ester	91	

Reaction condition: Cu10Ni10-PMO 0.1g, ethanol 3ml, Decane 20μl, 310 °C, 6h.

©: internal standard, *: compounds further confirmed by spiking with authentic standards. Quantification was performed based on additional GC-FID analysis using internal standard and calibration curves for compounds labeled with *

Only compounds with a similarity match higher than 80% based on GC-MS identification are listed. These accounted for a total area percentage >95%.

Table S5 Influence of temperature and catalyst loading on reaction performance using Cu10Ni10-PMO catalyst.

Entry	Tem. (°C)	Cat. loading (g)	Carbon balance (%)	Conv. %	Yield%								STY (g _{pro} kg _{cat} ⁻¹ h ⁻¹) ^a	Alcohols /esters	
					ButOH	AcOEt	HexOH	OctOH	EButOH	EB	EHexOH	AcOBut			
1	180	0.1	98.5	2.3	0.6(74) ^b	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	19.3	3.0
2	220	0.1	91.8	14.4	4.8(78)	0.8	0.4	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	152.9	5.9
3	270	0.1	86.2	30.0	12.2(74)	1.0	1.9	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.1	385.6	10.6
4	290	0.1	79.6	43.8	16.3(69)	1.6	3.3	0.7	0.8	0.4	0.2	0.3	0.3	518.7	9.3
5	310	0.1	81.2	47.9	21.1(72)	0.9	4.5	0.7	0.9	0.7	0.4	0.4	0.4	670.3	13.8
6	320	0.1	75.0	56.5	22.2(70)	1.0	5.2	0.9	1.1	0.8	0.3	0.3	0.3	704.6	14.1
7	310	0.05	78.2	45.2	16.6(70)	1.4	3.5	0.5	0.7	0.5	0.1	0.3	0.3	1056.4	11.3
8	310	0.2	68.0	62.2	19.6(68)	0.8	5.6	1.3	1.5	0.7	0.7	0.3	0.3	311.3	19.1

Reaction conditions: Ethanol 3ml, Decane 20µl as internal standard, 6h.

a. Space time yield of 1-butanol. b. Number in the bracket is the selectivity of 1-butanol.

ButOH: 1-Butanol, AcOEt: Ethyl Acetate, HexOH: 1-Hexanol, OctOH: 1-Octanol, EButOH: 2-Ethylbutanol, EB: Ethyl Butyrate, EHexOH: 2-Ethylhexanol, AcOBut: Butyl Acetate

Table S6 Catalyst recycling experiments.

Cycles	Conversion %	Yield%							
		ButOH	AcOEt	HexOH	OctOH	EButOH	EB	EHexOH	AcOBut
1	50.3	20.8(70) ^a	1.0	4.9	1.0	1.1	0.6	0.4	0.3
2	40.6	13.8(80)	0.5	2.2	0.2	0.4	0.3	0.1	0.1
3	37.5	13.5(81)	0.5	1.7	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.0
4	33.3	11.6(83)	0.4	1.3	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.0
5	31.3	11.8(83)	0.4	1.4	0.0	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.0
6	39.8	10.4(87)	0.3	1.1	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.0
7	37.8	9.6(84)	0.3	1.1	0.0	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.0

Reaction conditions: Cu10Ni10-PMO 0.1 g, ethanol 3ml, 310 °C, 6h, decane 20µl.

a. Number in the bracket is the selectivity of 1-butanol.

Table S7 Leaching tests during catalyst recycling for Cu10Ni10-PMO catalyst.

Cycles	Cu (mg/L) ^a	Mg (mg/L)	Al (mg/L)	Ni (mg/L)
1	0.4	8.3	2.9	0.1
4	0.2	2.0	2.8	0.1
7	0.2	1.6	3.5	0.1

a. Concentration is based on the solution after diluted by THF to 10ml.

Table S8 Quantitative data of NH₃-TPD and acid sites distribution.

Sample	NH ₃ uptake	Population of acid sites (%)			T _{max1}	T _{max2}	T _{max3}
	(mmol/g _{cat})	n ₁	n ₂	n ₃		(°C)	
Ni20-PMO	0.82	5	28	67	92	202	267
Cu20-PMO	0.83	2	35	62	88	253	312
Cu10Ni10-PMO	0.56	3	38	59	105	208	279
MgAl-PMO	1.33	3	22	76	104	208	328

Table S9 Quantitative data of CO₂-TPD and basic sites distribution.

Sample	CO ₂ uptake	Population of basic sites (%)		T _{max1}	T _{max2}
	(mmol/g _{cat})	n ₁	n ₂		(°C)
Ni20-PMO	0.61	24	76	211	277
Cu20-PMO	0.62	37	63	250	322
Cu10Ni10-PMO	0.41	23	77	218	272
MgAl-PMO	0.97	17	83	221	322

Figure S1 XRD patterns of Cu₁₀Ni₁₀-PMO catalyst after 1 cycle and 4 cycles.

Figure S2 NH₃-TPD (left) and CO₂-TPD (right) profiles of the investigated catalysts.

The distribution of binding sites with acidic properties was determined by temperature-programmed desorption (TPD) of NH₃ pre-adsorbed at room temperature. The TPD profile of all catalysts show that NH₃ desorbs in three overlapping peaks (Figure S1, left). These 3 different peaks account for the presence of sites of weak (W), medium (M) and high (H) acid strength, respectively. The amount of NH₃ desorbed at the different temperature steps allowed us to calculate the relative number of acid sites (Table S6). All samples mainly exhibited sites of medium and high binding with NH₃, accounting for the acidity of the synthesized mixed-oxides materials. The Cu-Ni-PMO is the composition with the lowest number of strong acidic sites (59%) and NH₃ uptake (0.56 mmol/g_{cat}) while the Mg-Al-PMO without any dopant shows the highest population of acidic binding sites (76%). Intermediate acidity values are found for the PMO compositions containing either only copper or nickel dopants.

Regarding the basic sites of the different PMO catalysts, CO₂-TPD measurements have been performed and the corresponding profiles, shown in Figure S1 (right), have been deconvoluted in two peaks. The total number of basic sites and the relative amount of sites with different basic strength are reported in Table S7. In analogy to the discussion of NH₃-TPD measurements, the PMO catalyst with no dopants has the highest basicity in addition to the highest number of acidic sites. The introduction of transition metal dopants instead of magnesium, drastically diminishes the CO₂ uptake, which reaches a minimum value (0.41 mmol/g_{cat}) for the catalyst containing copper and nickel dopants, lower than half of the value obtained for the Mg-Al-PMO.

Figure S3 Relationship between base/acid ratio and rate of butanol formation.

Figure S4 Product distributions in the self-coupling of primary alcohols catalyzed by Cu₁₀Ni₁₀-PMO catalyst. Reaction conditions: substrate (3 ml), Cu₁₀Ni₁₀-PMO (100mg), 310 °C, 6h.

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